

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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“SUSTAINABLE TOURISM”, “GREEN TOURISM” AND “ECO-TOURISM”: DIFFERENCES AND KEY PRINCIPLES

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Abstract: Tourism, a significant global economic activity, increasingly embraces sustainability to mitigate its environmental, social, and economic impacts. This paper explores the nuanced distinctions and underlying principles of three key concepts in responsible tourism: sustainable tourism, green tourism, and eco-tourism. Moreover, the paper provides some recommendations and list of tasks that should be implemented in order to advance the development of sustainable tourism, green tourism, and eco-tourism.

Key words: sustainable tourism, green tourism, eco-tourism, principles, conservation, community involvement.

Annotatsiya: Muhim global iqtisodiy faoliyat bo'lgan turizm o'zining salbiy ekologik, ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy ta'sirini yumshatish maqsadida barqaror rivojlanishga tobora ko'proq e'tibor qaratmoqda. Ushbu maqolada mas'uliyatli turizmning (responsible tourism) uchta asosiy turi bo'lgan barqaror turizm, “yashil” turizm ba ekoturizmning asosiy farqlari va birlamchi tamoyillari ko'rib chiqiladi. Bundan tashqari, maqolada mamlakatda barqaror turizm, “yashil” turizm va ekoturizmni rivojlantirishga ko'maklashish uchun bajarilishi kerak bo'lgan ba'zi tavsiyalar va vazifalar keltirib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: barqaror turizm, “yashil” turizm, ekoturizm, tamoyillar, tabiatni muhofaza qilish, jamoatchilikni jalb qilish.

Аннотация: Туризм, являющийся важной глобальной экономической деятельностью, все чаще ориентируется на устойчивое развитие для смягчения его экологических, социальных и экономических последствий. В данной статье рассматриваются нюансы различий и основополагающие принципы трех ключевых концепций ответственного туризма: устойчивого туризма, зеленого туризма и экотуризма. Кроме того, в документе приводятся некоторые рекомендации и перечень задач, которые должны быть выполнены для продвижения развития устойчивого туризма, зеленого туризма и экотуризма в стране.

Ключевые слова: устойчивый туризм, зеленый туризм, экотуризм, принципы, охрана природы, вовлечение сообщества.

INTRODUCTION

Tourism has evolved dramatically in recent decades, becoming one of the largest and fastest-growing economic sectors globally. Statistics shows that tourism and travel industry made up 9.1 percent of the global GDP in 2023 (Statista Research Department, 2024). This evolution is driven by various factors, including advancements in transportation and technology, changes in consumer behavior, and increased awareness of environmental and cultural sustainability. Thus, “sustainable tourism”, “green tourism” and “eco-tourism” have become crucial in the contemporary world due to growing environmental concerns, the socio-economic impacts of tourism, and the need for responsible development. These forms of tourism emphasize minimizing negative impacts on the environment and local communities while maximizing economic benefits and cultural preservation. Sustainable tourism, a concept closely aligned with green tourism and ecotourism, aims to mitigate the negative impacts of tourism while enhancing its positive effects. It integrates environmental, economic, and social dimensions to promote long-term sustainability. The concept has gained prominence as stakeholders recognize the need to balance tourism development with environmental conservation and community well-being (Weaver, 2006). Green tourism has gained significant attention over the past few decades. This form of tourism emphasizes responsible travel to natural areas, conservation of the environment, and improvement of the well-being of local people. The concept intersects with various disciplines, including environmental

science, economics, and social studies. Eco-tourism, a subset of sustainable tourism, emphasizes responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment, sustains the well-being of local people, and involves interpretation and education (Fennell, 2008).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of sustainable tourism emerged in response to the growing awareness of environmental degradation and social inequities caused by mass tourism. The 1987 Brundtland Report, "Our Common Future" was a pivotal document that highlighted the need for sustainable development, including in the tourism sector. The 1992 Earth Summit in Rio de Janeiro further emphasized sustainable tourism as part of the broader sustainable development agenda. Sustainable tourism is defined by the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) as "tourism that takes full account of its current and future economic, social, and environmental impacts, addressing the needs of visitors, the industry, the environment, and host communities" (UNWTO, 2005). It encompasses a wide range of practices designed to make tourism more sustainable at various levels, from local initiatives to global policies. Hall and Lew (2009) define sustainable tourism as a form of tourism that satisfies the criteria of being ecologically sustainable in the long term, economically viable, as well as ethically and socially equitable".

The roots of green tourism can be traced back to the 1960s and 1970s, a period marked by growing environmental awareness and the birth of the modern environmental movement. This era saw the publication of influential works such as Rachel Carson's "Silent Spring" (1962) and the establishment of environmental organizations like Greenpeace. The concept gained further traction in the 1980s and 1990s with the advent of sustainable development frameworks, most notably the Brundtland Report (1987), which emphasized the need for development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Green tourism is broadly defined as tourism that seeks to minimize environmental impacts, promote conservation, and foster sustainable development. The International Ecotourism Society (TIES) defines ecotourism as "responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment, sustains the well-being of the local people, and involves interpretation and education" (TIES, 2015). According to Higham and Cohen (2011), "Green tourism is tourism that prioritizes environmental protection and sustainability, seeking to minimize the environmental footprint of tourism activities through various means, including sustainable transportation, eco-friendly accommodations, and environmentally conscious behaviors by tourists".

The concept of eco-tourism emerged in the late 20th century alongside the broader environmental movement. The 1980s and 1990s saw a surge in environmental awareness, leading to the establishment of numerous environmental organizations and the publication of influential works on sustainable development. The term "eco-tourism" was popularized during this period, reflecting a shift towards more responsible and sustainable travel practices. The International Ecotourism Society (TIES) defines eco-tourism as "responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment, sustains the well-being of local people, and involves interpretation and education" (TIES, 2015). The scope of eco-tourism encompasses a variety of activities such as wildlife viewing, hiking, cultural exchanges, and conservation projects, all designed to have minimal impact on the environment and benefit local communities. This form of tourism has gained traction as tourists and industry stakeholders increasingly recognize the importance of environmental conservation and sustainable development (Honey, 2008). Eco-tourism aims to have a minimal environmental footprint and support conservation efforts. Revenue from eco-tourism can be used to fund protected areas and conservation projects, contributing to the preservation of ecosystems and wildlife (Wearing, S., & Neil, J., 2009). According to Buckley (2009), "Ecotourism is defined as tourism to natural areas that interprets local environments and cultures, supports the conservation of these areas, and sustains the livelihoods of local people. It aims to be ecologically, socially, and economically sustainable".

METHODS AND METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative research design to explore the differences and key principles of sustainable tourism, green tourism, and eco-tourism. The research methodology includes a comprehensive literature review. A systematic literature review was conducted to gather existing knowledge and theoretical frameworks related to sustainable tourism, green tourism, and eco-tourism. Academic journals, books, industry reports, and reputable online sources were reviewed to identify definitions, principles and practices.

DISCUSSION

Sustainable tourism, green tourism, and eco-tourism are all forms of tourism that emphasize environmental responsibility and sustainability, but they have distinct focuses and characteristics. Each type of tourism has its

own specific practices and goals, but they all contribute to the broader aim of making tourism more responsible and sustainable (Table 1).

Key characteristics of **sustainable tourism**:

- *Broad Focus*: Includes economic, social, and environmental aspects.
- *Long-Term Planning*: Aims to minimize negative impacts and maximize benefits over the long term.
- *Community Involvement*: Engages local communities in planning and decision-making.
- *Resource Efficiency*: Promotes the efficient use of resources and reducing waste.
- Key characteristics of **green tourism**:
- *Environmental Focus*: Prioritizes reducing environmental impacts, such as carbon emissions, waste, and water usage.
- *Eco-Friendly Practices*: Encourages the use of renewable energy, recycling, and conservation efforts.
- *Certification and Standards*: Often involves certification schemes (e.g., Green Key, Green Globe) to validate eco-friendly practices.
- Key characteristics of **eco-tourism**:
- *Nature-Based*: Involves travel to natural areas, often with an emphasis on wildlife and natural habitats.
- *Conservation and Education*: Aims to support conservation efforts and educate tourists about environmental issues.
- *Minimizing Impact*: Emphasizes low-impact travel and activities that do not harm the environment.

Table 1. Comparison of sustainable tourism, green tourism and eco-tourism*

Aspect	Sustainable Tourism	Green Tourism	Eco-Tourism
Scope	Broad (environmental, economic, social)	Primarily environmental	Specific to natural areas
Focus	Long-term sustainability	Environmentally friendly practices	Nature conservation and local benefits
Community Involvement	High	Moderate	High
Scale	All types of tourism	Varies	Usually small scale
Certifications	Various sustainability certifications	Green certifications	Often involves eco-certifications
Education	Promotes awareness in all aspects	Environmental awareness	Environmental and cultural education

*Made by author

By understanding these differences, stakeholders can better align their efforts with the specific goals and practices of each type of tourism.

RESULTS

The concepts of sustainable tourism, green tourism, and eco-tourism share a common goal of reducing the negative impacts of tourism and promoting environmental stewardship. However, each approach has distinct principles and areas of focus (Table 2). While sustainable tourism, green tourism, and eco-tourism share overlapping goals, they differ in scope and focus. Sustainable tourism encompasses a comprehensive approach addressing environmental, economic, and social sustainability. Green tourism narrows its focus to eco-friendly practices within the tourism sector. Eco-tourism, on the other hand, zeroes in on conservation and education within natural settings. Understanding these distinctions helps stakeholders implement appropriate strategies to achieve the desired outcomes in their tourism initiatives.

Table 2. Key principles of sustainable tourism, green tourism and eco-tourism*

Sustainable tourism	Environmental Integrity	Ensuring that tourism activities minimize negative impacts on the environment. This includes conserving natural resources, reducing pollution, and protecting biodiversity.
	Economic Viability	Promoting economic growth and stability through tourism while ensuring that benefits are distributed equitably among stakeholders.
	Social Equity	Ensuring that tourism respects the socio-cultural authenticity of host communities, promotes cross-cultural understanding, and contributes to the social well-being of local populations.
	Long-term Perspective	Planning and managing tourism development with a long-term perspective to ensure that future generations can enjoy and benefit from tourism resources.
Green tourism	Minimizing Environmental Impact	Green tourism practices aim to reduce the ecological footprint of tourism activities. This includes promoting energy efficiency, waste reduction, and the use of renewable resources.
	Conservation Efforts	Tourism can play a crucial role in conservation by generating funds for protected areas, wildlife reserves, and environmental education programs.
	Community Involvement and Benefits	Green tourism seeks to involve local communities in decision-making processes and ensure that they benefit economically and socially.
	Education and Awareness	A key component of green tourism is educating tourists about the environment, local cultures, and conservation issues.
Eco-tourism	Environmental Conservation	Eco-tourism aims to minimize environmental impact and promote conservation efforts.
	Community Involvement	Eco-tourism seeks to involve local communities in tourism planning and operations, ensuring that they benefit economically and socially.
	Educational Experience	A central component of eco-tourism is education. Tourists are educated about the natural and cultural heritage of the destinations they visit, fostering greater awareness and appreciation for conservation efforts.
	Sustainable Practices	Eco-tourism promotes sustainable practices such as reducing waste, conserving water and energy, and using environmentally friendly materials and technologies.

*Made by author

CONCLUSION

Sustainable tourism represents a holistic approach to tourism development that seeks to balance economic growth, environmental protection, and social equity. By addressing the challenges and leveraging the opportunities associated with sustainable tourism, stakeholders can contribute to a more sustainable and resilient tourism industry that benefits both people and the planet. Green tourism and sustainable tourism are vital in today's world as they address the pressing environmental, economic, and social challenges associated with conventional tourism. By promoting responsible practices, supporting conservation efforts, and fostering community well-being, these forms of tourism contribute to a more sustainable and equitable future. Embracing and advancing sustainable tourism practices will be crucial in ensuring the long-term viability and positive impact of the tourism industry on our planet and its inhabitants. Eco-tourism represents a promising approach to achieving sustainable development goals by balancing environmental conservation, community well-being, and economic benefits. While there are challenges to overcome, continued efforts to promote genuine sustainability practices and involve local communities will be key to realizing the full potential of eco-tourism.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To advance sustainable tourism, green tourism and eco-tourism stakeholders can focus on the following key areas:

- *Policy and Regulation:* Strengthening policies and regulations to ensure that tourism development aligns with sustainability goals.

- *Education and Awareness:* Educating tourists, businesses, and local communities about the importance of sustainable tourism and how they can contribute.
- *Innovation and Technology:* Leveraging technology and innovation to develop sustainable tourism solutions, such as smart tourism systems and eco-friendly infrastructure.
- *Collaboration and Partnerships:* Fostering collaboration among governments, businesses, non-governmental organizations, and local communities to promote sustainable tourism practices.
- *Strengthening Certification and Standards:* Developing robust certification schemes and standards to ensure genuine sustainability practices.
- *Enhanced Community Engagement:* Involving local communities in tourism planning and decision-making processes to ensure their needs and perspectives are considered.
- *Research and Monitoring:* Conducting ongoing research and monitoring to assess the impacts of tourism and develop adaptive management strategies.

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